

The applications of definite 2-refined neutrosophic integrals

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Abstract: The objective of this article is to study the applications of definite 2-refined neutrosophic integrals, where we introduced set of theories related to the applications of definite 2-refined neutrosophic integrals, such as area, length of 2-refined neutrosophic curve and volumes.

Keywords: integrals; area; 2-refined neutrosophic; curves; length; volume.

1. Introduction and Preliminaries

As a mathematical framework intended to manage several types of uncertainty, such as vagueness, ambiguity, imprecision, incompleteness, inconsistency, redundancy, and contradiction, Smarandache proposed Neutrosophic Logic in contrast to conventional logical systems. This logic is part of a broader philosophical approach he called neutrosophy [4]. Within this framework, he defined the standard form of neutrosophic real numbers [3–5] and developed the foundation for neutrosophic statistics [5–6]. On the other hand, refined neutrosophic numbers studied by Smarandache [1].

Additional, advancements in neutrosophic differentiation and integration contributed by Y. Alhasan [2, 8–11, 13]. Agboola studied the refined neutrosophic algebraic structures [15].

Adeleke, Agboola and Smarandache introduced the refined neutrosophic rings I [16]. Moreover, the AH isometry was employed to investigate a range of mathematical structures, including conic sections, concepts in real analysis, and geometric surfaces [10, 14].

One of the most significant applications of integration in human life is the computation of area, volume, and arc length. There are aspects of our world characterized by a degree of uncertainty that cannot be accurately described through simple means. Therefore, it had to be studied according to the neutrosophic logic.

2. The applications of definite 2-refined neutrosophic integrals

2.1 The area under 2-refined neutrosophic curves

Theorem 1

Let $f(x, I_1, I_2)$ be a continuous neutrosophic function defined in the interval $[a_0 + a_1I_1 + a_2I_2, b_0 + b_1I_1 + b_2I_2]$. Then the area of the region below the neutrosophic curve of $f(x, I_1, I_2)$, above the x – axis, between $x = a_0 + a_1I_1 + a_2I_2$ and $x = b_0 + b_1I_1 + b_2I_2$, is given by formula:

$$A = \int_{a_0+a_1I_1+a_2I_2}^{b_0+b_1I_1+b_2I_2} |f(x, I_1, I_2)| dx$$

Where $a_0, a_1, a_2, b_0, b_1, b_2$ are real numbers, I_1, I_2 represent indeterminacy.

Theorem 2

Let $g(y, I_1, I_2)$ be a continuous neutrosophic function defined in the interval $[c_0 + c_1I_1 + c_2I_2, d_0 + d_1I_1 + d_2I_2]$. Then the area of the region below the neutrosophic curve of $g(y, I_1, I_2)$, above the y – axis, between $y = c_0 + c_1I_1 + c_2I_2$ and $y = d_0 + d_1I_1 + d_2I_2$, is given by formula:

$$A = \int_{c_0+c_1I_1+c_2I_2}^{d_0+d_1I_1+d_2I_2} |g(y, I_1, I_2)| dy$$

Where $c_0, c_1, c_2, d_0, d_1, d_2$ are real numbers, I_1, I_2 represent indeterminacy.

Example 1

Let’s find the area of the region bounded by $f(x, I_1, I_2) = 2x + 2 + I_1 + 3I_2$, the x – axis and the lines $x = 1 - 2I_1 + I_2$ and $x = 2 + 3I_1 + 2I_2$.

$$\begin{aligned} A &= \int_{a_0+a_1I_1+a_2I_2}^{b_0+b_1I_1+b_2I_2} |f(x, I_1, I_2)| dx = \int_{1-2I_1+I_2}^{2+3I_1+2I_2} |2x + 2 + I_1 + 3I_2| dx \\ \Rightarrow A &= \int_{1-2I_1+I_2}^{2+3I_1+2I_2} |2x + 2 + I_1 + 3I_2| dx = [x^2 + (2 + I_1 + 3I_2)x]_{1-2I_1+I_2}^{2+3I_1+2I_2} \\ &= [(2 + 3I_1 + 2I_2)^2 + (2 + I_1 + 3I_2)(2 + 3I_1 + 2I_2)] - [(1 - 2I_1 + I_2)^2 + (2 + I_1 + 3I_2)(1 - 2I_1 + I_2)] \\ &= 8 + 61I_1 + 22I_2 - 3 + 11I_1 - 8I_2 = 5 + 72I_1 + 14I_2 > 0 \end{aligned}$$

Where: $5 > 0$, $5 + 14 = 19 > 0$ and $5 + 72 + 14 = 91 > 0$

2.2 Area between two 2-refined neutrosophic curves

Theorem 3 (Area between two 2-refined neutrosophic curves (attributed to the x – axis))

The area A of the region bounded by the curves $f(x, I_1, I_2), g(x, I_1, I_2)$, and the lines $x = a_0 + a_1I_1 + a_2I_2$ and $x = b_0 + b_1I_1 + b_2I_2$ ($b_0 > a_0$, $b_0 + b_2 > a_0 + a_2$ and $b_0 + b_1 + b_2 > a_0 + a_1 + a_2$), where $f(x, I_1, I_2)$ and $g(x, I_1, I_2)$ are continuous and $f(x, I_1, I_2) \geq g(x, I_1, I_2)$ for all x in $[a_0 + a_1I_1 + a_2I_2, b_0 + b_1I_1 + b_2I_2]$, is given by formula:

$$A = \int_{a_0+a_1I_1+a_2I_2}^{b_0+b_1I_1+b_2I_2} [f(x, I_1, I_2) - g(x, I_1, I_2)] dx$$

Theorem 4 (Area between two 2-refined neutrosophic curves (attributed to the $y - axis$))

The area A of the region bounded by the curves $w(y, I_1, I_2), v(y, I_1, I_2)$, and the lines $y = c_0 + c_1I_1 + c_2I_2$ and $y = d_0 + d_1I_1 + d_2I_2$ ($d_0 > c_0, d_0 + d_2 > c_0 + c_2$ and $d_0 + d_1 + d_2 > c_0 + c_1 + c_2$), where $f(y, I_1, I_2)$ and $g(y, I_1, I_2)$ are continuous and $w(y, I_1, I_2) \geq v(y, I_1, I_2)$ for all x in $[c_0 + c_1I_1 + c_2I_2, d_0 + d_1I_1 + d_2I_2]$, is given by formula:

$$A = \int_{c_0+c_1I_1+c_2I_2}^{d_0+d_1I_1+d_2I_2} [w(y, I_1, I_2) - v(y, I_1, I_2)] dy$$

Example 2

Let find the area of the region bounded by $y = e^{x+I_1+2I_2}$, $y = 2x - I_1 + 3I_2$, and the lines $x = 0, x = 1 + 2I_1 + I_2$.

Solution:

$y = e^{x+I_1+2I_2} > y = 2x - I_1 + 3I_2$ on $[0, 1 + 2I_1 + I_2]$, then:

$$\begin{aligned} A &= \int_0^{1+2I_1+I_2} [e^{x+I_1+2I_2} - 2x + I_1 - 3I_2] dx = [e^{x+I_1+2I_2} - x^2 + (I_1 - 3I_2)x]_0^{1+2I_1+I_2} \\ &= [e^{1+2I_1+I_2+I_1+2I_2} - (1 + 2I_1 + I_2)^2 + (I_1 - 3I_2)(1 + 2I_1 + I_2)] - [e^{I_1+2I_2}] \\ &= e^{1+3I_1+3I_2} - 1 - I_1 + I_2 - 2I_1 - 6I_2 - e^{I_1+2I_2} = e^{1+3I_1+3I_2} - e^{I_1+2I_2} - 1 - 3I_1 - 5I_2 \\ &= e + I_1[e^7 - e^4] + I_2[e^4 - e] - (1 + I_1[e^3 - e^2] + I_2[e^2 - 1]) - 1 - 3I_1 - 5I_2 \\ &= e - 2 + (e^7 - e^3 - e^4 + e^2 - 3)I_1 + (e^4 - e^2 - e - 4)I_2 \end{aligned}$$

Clearly that $e - 2 + (e^7 - e^3 - e^4 + e^2 - 3)I_1 + (e^4 - e^2 - e - 4)I_2 > 0$ where: $e - 2 > 0, e^4 - e^2 - 6 > 0$ and $e^7 - e^3 - 9 > 0$

Example 3

Evaluate the area of the region bounded by $x = y^2$, $x = (-3 - 2I_1 - I_2)y - 2 - I_2$, and the lines $y = -2 + (2\sqrt{6} - 2)I_1 + I_2, y = -1 + (\sqrt{6} - 2)I_1$

Solution:

$x = y^2 \geq x = (-3 - 2I_1 - I_2)y - 2 - I_2$ on $[-2 + (2\sqrt{6} - 2)I_1 + I_2, -1 + (\sqrt{6} - 2)I_1]$, then:

$$A = \int_{-2+(2\sqrt{6}-2)I_1+I_2}^{-1+(\sqrt{6}-2)I_1} [y^2 + (-3 - 2I_1 - I_2)y - 2 - I_2] dy$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \left[\frac{y^3}{3} + \frac{(-3 - 2I_1 - I_2)}{2} y^2 + (-2 - I_2)y \right]_{-2+(2\sqrt{6}-2)I_1+I_2}^{-1+(\sqrt{6}-2)I_1} \\
 &= \left[\frac{(-1 + (\sqrt{6} - 2)I_1)^3}{3} + \frac{(-3 - 2I_1 - I_2)}{2} (-1 + (\sqrt{6} - 2)I_1)^2 + (-2 - I_2)(-1 + (\sqrt{6} - 2)I_1) \right] \\
 &\quad - \left[\frac{(-2 + (2\sqrt{6} - 2)I_1 + I_2)^3}{3} + \frac{(-3 - 2I_1 - I_2)}{2} (-2 + (2\sqrt{6} - 2)I_1 + I_2)^2 \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + (-2 - I_2)(-2 + (2\sqrt{6} - 2)I_1 + I_2) \right] \\
 &= \left[\frac{-1}{3} + \frac{33\sqrt{6} - 80}{3} I_1 - \frac{3}{2} + (-43 + 18\sqrt{6})I_1 + \frac{1}{2} I_2 + 2 + (-3\sqrt{6} + 6)I_1 + I_2 \right] \\
 &\quad - \left[-\frac{8}{3} + \left(\frac{128\sqrt{6}}{3} - 64 \right) I_1 - \frac{28}{3} I_2 - 6 + (-80 + 36\sqrt{6})I_1 - 72I_2 + 4 + (6 - 6\sqrt{6})I_1 \right. \\
 &\quad \left. - I_2 \right] \\
 &= \frac{29}{6} + \left(\frac{223}{3} + \frac{76}{3}\sqrt{6} \right) I_1 + \frac{491}{6} I_2
 \end{aligned}$$

2.3 Length of 2-refined neutrosophic curve

Definition 1

If $y = f(x, I_1, I_2)$ is a smooth curve on the interval $[a_0 + a_1I_1 + a_2I_2, b_0 + b_1I_1 + b_2I_2]$, then the arc length L_f of this curve over $[a_0 + a_1I_1 + a_2I_2, b_0 + b_1I_1 + b_2I_2]$ is defined as:

$$L_f = \int_{a_0+a_1I_1+a_2I_2}^{b_0+b_1I_1+b_2I_2} \sqrt{1 + [f'(x, I_1, I_2)]^2} dx$$

Definition 2

If $x = g(y, I_1, I_2)$ is a smooth curve on the interval $[c_0 + c_1I_1 + c_2I_2, d_0 + d_1I_1 + d_2I_2]$, then the arc length L_g of this curve over $[c_0 + c_1I_1 + c_2I_2, d_0 + d_1I_1 + d_2I_2]$ is defined as:

$$L_g = \int_{c_0+c_1I_1+c_2I_2}^{d_0+d_1I_1+d_2I_2} \sqrt{1 + [g'(y, I_1, I_2)]^2} dy$$

Example 4

Let's find the arc length of the curve of $y = f(x, I_1, I_2) = \ln \left(\sec \left(x + \frac{\pi}{4} I_1 + \frac{\pi}{4} I_2 \right) \right)$ on the interval $\left[0, \frac{\pi}{4} + \frac{\pi}{4} I_1 + \frac{\pi}{4} I_2 \right]$.

$$f(x, I_1, I_2) = \ln \left(\sec \left(x + \frac{\pi}{4} I_1 + \frac{\pi}{4} I_2 \right) \right) \Rightarrow f'(x, I_1, I_2) = \tan \left(x + \frac{\pi}{4} I_1 + \frac{\pi}{4} I_2 \right)$$

$$L = \int_{a_0+a_1I_1+a_2I_2}^{b_0+b_1I_1+b_2I_2} \sqrt{1 + [f'(x, I_1, I_2)]^2} dx$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 L &= \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4} + \frac{\pi}{4}I_1 + \frac{\pi}{4}I_2} \sqrt{1 + \tan^2 \left(x + \frac{\pi}{4}I_1 + \frac{\pi}{4}I_2 \right)} dx \\
 &= \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4} + \frac{\pi}{4}I_1 + \frac{\pi}{4}I_2} \sqrt{\sec^2 \left(x + \frac{\pi}{4}I_1 + \frac{\pi}{4}I_2 \right)} dx \\
 &= \int_{-\frac{\pi}{4}}^{\frac{\pi}{4} + \frac{\pi}{4}I_1 + \frac{\pi}{4}I_2} \sec \left(x + \frac{\pi}{4}I_1 + \frac{\pi}{4}I_2 \right) dx = \left[\ln \left| \sec \left(x + \frac{\pi}{4}I_1 + \frac{\pi}{4}I_2 \right) + \tan \left(x + \frac{\pi}{4}I_1 + \frac{\pi}{4}I_2 \right) \right| \right]_{-\frac{\pi}{4}}^{\frac{\pi}{4} + \frac{\pi}{4}I_1 + \frac{\pi}{4}I_2} \\
 &= \left[\ln \left| \sec \left(\frac{\pi}{4} + \frac{\pi}{2}I_1 + \frac{\pi}{2}I_2 \right) + \tan \left(\frac{\pi}{4} + \frac{\pi}{2}I_1 + \frac{\pi}{2}I_2 \right) \right| \right] \\
 &\quad - \left[\ln \left| \sec \left(-\frac{\pi}{4} + \frac{\pi}{4}I_1 + \frac{\pi}{4}I_2 \right) + \tan \left(-\frac{\pi}{4} + \frac{\pi}{4}I_1 + \frac{\pi}{4}I_2 \right) \right| \right] \\
 &= \left[\ln \left| \sec \left(\frac{\pi}{4} \right) + \left[\sec \left(\frac{\pi}{4} + \pi \right) - \sec \left(\frac{3\pi}{4} \right) \right] I_1 + \left[\sec \left(\frac{3\pi}{4} \right) - \sec \left(\frac{\pi}{4} \right) \right] I_2 + \tan \left(\frac{\pi}{4} \right) \right. \right. \\
 &\quad \left. \left. + \left[\tan \left(\frac{\pi}{4} + \pi \right) - \tan \left(\frac{3\pi}{4} \right) \right] I_1 + \left[\tan \left(\frac{3\pi}{4} \right) - \tan \left(\frac{\pi}{4} \right) \right] I_2 \right| \right] \\
 &\quad - \left[\ln \left| \sec \left(-\frac{\pi}{4} \right) + \left[\sec \left(\frac{\pi}{4} \right) - \sec(0) \right] I_1 + \left[\sec(0) - \sec \left(-\frac{\pi}{4} \right) \right] I_2 + \tan \left(-\frac{\pi}{4} \right) \right. \right. \\
 &\quad \left. \left. + \left[\tan \left(\frac{\pi}{4} \right) - \tan(0) \right] I_1 + \left[\tan(0) - \tan \left(-\frac{\pi}{4} \right) \right] I_2 \right| \right] \\
 &= \left[\ln \left| \sqrt{2} - 2\sqrt{2}I_1 - 2\sqrt{2}I_2 + 1 - 2I_1 - 2I_2 \right| \right] - \left[\ln \left| \sqrt{2} + (\sqrt{2} - 1)I_1 + (1 - \sqrt{2})I_2 - 1 + I_1 + I_2 \right| \right] \\
 &= \left[\ln \left| (\sqrt{2} + 1) + (-2\sqrt{2} - 2)I_1 + (-2\sqrt{2} - 2)I_2 \right| \right] - \left[\ln \left| (\sqrt{2} - 1) + \sqrt{2}I_1 + (2 - \sqrt{2})I_2 \right| \right] \\
 &= \ln \left[\sqrt{2} + 1 + (2 + 2\sqrt{2})I_1 + (3\sqrt{2} + 3)I_2 \right] - \ln \left[\left| \sqrt{2} - 1 + \sqrt{2}I_1 + (3 - 2\sqrt{2})I_2 \right| \right] \\
 &= \ln(\sqrt{2} + 1) + (\ln(6\sqrt{2} + 6) - \ln(4\sqrt{2} + 4))I_1 + (\ln(4\sqrt{2} + 4) - \ln(1 + \sqrt{2}))I_2 \\
 &\quad - [\ln(\sqrt{2} - 1) + (\ln 2 - \ln(3 - \sqrt{2}))I_1 + (\ln(3 - \sqrt{2}) - \ln(\sqrt{2} - 1))I_2] \\
 &= \ln(\sqrt{2} + 1) - \ln(\sqrt{2} - 1) + [\ln(6\sqrt{2} + 6) - \ln(4\sqrt{2} + 4) - \ln 2 + \ln(3 - \sqrt{2})]I_1 \\
 &\quad + [\ln(4\sqrt{2} + 4) - \ln(1 + \sqrt{2}) - \ln(3 - \sqrt{2}) + \ln(\sqrt{2} - 1)]I_2 > 0
 \end{aligned}$$

Where:

$$\ln(\sqrt{2} + 1) - \ln(\sqrt{2} - 1) > 0$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\ln(\sqrt{2} + 1) - \ln(\sqrt{2} - 1) + \ln(6\sqrt{2} + 6) - \ln(4\sqrt{2} + 4) - \ln 2 + \ln(3 - \sqrt{2}) + \ln(4\sqrt{2} + 4) \\
 &\quad - \ln(1 + \sqrt{2}) - \ln(3 - \sqrt{2}) + \ln(\sqrt{2} - 1) > 0
 \end{aligned}$$

and $\ln(\sqrt{2} + 1) - \ln(\sqrt{2} - 1) + \ln(4\sqrt{2} + 4) - \ln(1 + \sqrt{2}) - \ln(3 - \sqrt{2}) + \ln(\sqrt{2} - 1) > 0$

4.4 Volumes of 2-refined neutrosophic revolution

Definition 3

Suppose that $f(x, I_1, I_2) \geq 0$ and it is continuous on the interval $[a_0 + a_1I_1 + a_2I_2, b_0 + b_1I_1 + b_2I_2]$, the volume of the resulting solid of revolution the region under the curve $y = f(x, I_1, I_2)$ for the interval $[a_0 + a_1I_1 + a_2I_2, b_0 + b_1I_1 + b_2I_2]$ about $x - axis$ is given by:

$$V_f = \int_{a_0+a_1I_1+a_2I_2}^{b_0+b_1I_1+b_2I_2} \pi [f(x, I_1, I_2)]^2 dx$$

Definition 4

Suppose that $g(y, I_1, I_2) \geq 0$ and it is continuous on the interval $[c_0 + c_1I_1 + c_2I_2, d_0 + d_1I_1 + d_2I_2]$, the volume of the resulting solid of revolution the region under the curve $x = g(y, I_1, I_2)$ for the interval $[c_0 + c_1I_1 + c_2I_2, d_0 + d_1I_1 + d_2I_2]$ about $y - axis$ is given by:

$$V_g = \int_{c_0+c_1I_1+c_2I_2}^{d_0+d_1I_1+d_2I_2} \pi [g(y, I_1, I_2)]^2 dy$$

Example 5

Let $f(x, I_1, I_2) = \sqrt{x + 5 - I_1 + 4I_2}$ find the volume of the solid resulting from rotating the region bounded by the curve of $f(x, I_1, I_2)$ about $x - axis$ from $x = 0$ to $x = 3 + 2I_1 + I_2$

$$\begin{aligned} V_f &= \int_{a_0+a_1I_1+a_2I_2}^{b_0+b_1I_1+b_2I_2} \pi [f(x, I_1, I_2)]^2 dx = \int_0^{3+2I_1+I_2} \pi [\sqrt{x + 5 - I_1 + 4I_2}]^2 dx \\ &= \int_0^{3+2I_1+I_2} \pi [x + 5 - I_1 + 4I_2] dx = \pi \left[\frac{x^2}{2} + (5 - I_1 + 4I_2)x \right]_0^{3+2I_1+I_2} \\ &= \pi \left[\frac{(3 + 2I_1 + I_2)^2}{2} + (5 - I_1 + 4I_2)(3 + 2I_1 + I_2) \right] \\ &= \left(\frac{9}{2} + 9I_1 + \frac{5}{2}I_2 + 15 + 24I_1 + 21I_2 \right) \pi \\ &= \left(\frac{39}{2} + 33I_1 + \frac{47}{2}I_2 \right) \pi \end{aligned}$$

Where:

$$\frac{39}{2} > 0, \frac{39}{2} + 33 + \frac{47}{2} > 0 \text{ and } \frac{39}{2} + \frac{47}{2} > 0$$

Example 6

Let $g(y, I_1, I_2) = \sqrt{-y + 6 + 2I_1 + 4I_2}$ find the volume of the solid resulting from rotating the region bounded by the curves of $g(y, I_1, I_2)$ about $y - axis$ from $y = 2 + 2I_1 + 2I_2$ to $y = 5 + 5I_1 + 5I_2$.

$$V_g = \int_{c_0+c_1I_1+c_2I_2}^{d_0+d_1I_1+d_2I_2} \pi [g(y, I_1, I_2)]^2 dy = \int_{2+2I_1+2I_2}^{5+5I_1+5I_2} \pi [\sqrt{-y + 6 + 2I_1 + 4I_2}]^2 dy$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \int_{2+2I_1+2I_2}^{5+5I_1+5I_2} \pi[-y + 6 + 2I_1 + 4I_2]dy = \pi \left[-\frac{y^2}{2} + (6 + 2I_1 + 4I_2)y \right]_{2+2I_1+2I_2}^{5+5I_1+5I_2} \\
 &= \pi \left[-\frac{(5 + 5I_1 + 5I_2)^2}{2} + (6 + 2I_1 + 4I_2)(5 + 5I_1 + 5I_2) + \frac{(2 + 2I_1 + 2I_2)^2}{2} \right. \\
 &\quad \left. - (6 + 2I_1 + 4I_2)(2 + 2I_1 + 2I_2) \right] \\
 &= \pi \left[-\frac{25}{2} - 50I_1 - 25I_2 + 30 + 80I_1 + 50I_2 + 2 + 8I_1 + 4I_2 - 12 - 32I_1 - 28I_2 \right] \\
 &= \left(\frac{15}{2} + 6I_1 + I_2 \right) \pi
 \end{aligned}$$

Where:

$$\frac{15}{2} > 0, \frac{15}{2} + 6 + 1 > 0 \text{ and } \frac{15}{2} + 1 > 0$$

Definition 5

Suppose that $f(x, I_1, I_2), g(x, I_1, I_2)$ are continuous and non-negative on the interval $[a_0 + a_1I_1 + a_2I_2, b_0 + b_1I_1 + b_2I_2]$, and $f(x, I_1, I_2) \geq g(x, I_1, I_2)$ for all x in the interval $[a_0 + a_1I_1 + a_2I_2, b_0 + b_1I_1 + b_2I_2]$, the volume of the resulting solid of revolution the region bounded between tow the curves $f(x, I_1, I_2), g(x, I_1, I_2)$ for the interval $[a_0 + a_1I_1 + a_2I_2, b_0 + b_1I_1 + b_2I_2]$ about $x - axis$ is given by:

$$V_{fg} = \int_{a_0+a_1I_1+a_2I_2}^{b_0+b_1I_1+b_2I_2} \pi([f(x, I_1, I_2)]^2 - [g(x, I_1, I_2)]^2) dx$$

Definition 6

Suppose that $w(y, I_1, I_2), v(y, I_1, I_2)$ are continuous and non-negative on the interval $[c_0 + c_1I_1 + c_2I_2, d_0 + d_1I_1 + d_2I_2]$, and $w(y, I_1, I_2) \geq v(y, I_1, I_2)$ for all x in the interval $[c_0 + c_1I_1 + c_2I_2, d_0 + d_1I_1 + d_2I_2]$, the volume of the resulting solid of revolution the region bounded between tow the curves $w(y, I_1, I_2), v(y, I_1, I_2)$ for the interval $[c_0 + c_1I_1 + c_2I_2, d_0 + d_1I_1 + d_2I_2]$ about $y - axis$ is given by:

$$V_{wv} = \int_{c_0+c_1I_1+c_2I_2}^{d_0+d_1I_1+d_2I_2} \pi([w(y, I_1, I_2)]^2 - [v(y, I_1, I_2)]^2) dy$$

Example 7

Find the volume of the solid resulting from rotating the region bounded between tow the curves $f(x, I_1, I_2) = x^2 + 2I_1 + 2I_2$ and $g(x, I_1, I_2) = x + 2I_1 + 2I_2$ from $x = 1 + I_1 + I_2$ to $x = 6 + 4I_1 + 2I_2$ about $x - axis$.

$$f(x, I_1, I_2) > g(x, I_1, I_2) \text{ on } [1 + I_1 + I_2, 6 + 4I_1 + 2I_2]$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 V &= \int_{a_0+a_1I_1+a_2I_2}^{b_0+b_1I_1+b_2I_2} \pi([f(x, I_1, I_2)]^2 - [g(x, I_1, I_2)]^2) dx \\
 &= \int_{1+I_1+I_2}^{6+4I_1+2I_2} \pi([x^2 + 2I_1 + 2I_2]^2 - [x + 2I_1 + 2I_2]^2) dx \\
 &= \int_{1+I_1+I_2}^{6+4I_1+2I_2} \pi([x^4 + (4I_1 + 4I_2)x^2 + 12I_1 + 4I_2] - [x^2 + (4I_1 + 4I_2)x + 12I_1 + 4I_2]) dx \\
 &= \int_{1+I_1+I_2}^{6+4I_1+2I_2} \pi[x^4 + (-1 + 4I_1 + 4I_2)x^2 - (4I_1 + 4I_2)x] dx \\
 &= \pi[x^4 + (-1 + 4I_1 + 4I_2)x^2 - (4I_1 + 4I_2)x]_{1+I_1+I_2}^{6+4I_1+2I_2} \\
 &= \pi \left[\left(\frac{(6 + 4I_1 + 2I_2)^5}{5} + (-1 + 4I_1 + 4I_2) \frac{(6 + 4I_1 + 2I_2)^3}{3} - (4I_1 + 4I_2)(6 + 4I_1 + 2I_2)^2 \right) \right. \\
 &\quad \left. - \left(\frac{(1 + I_1 + I_2)^5}{5} + (-1 + 4I_1 + 4I_2) \frac{(1 + I_1 + I_2)^3}{3} - (4I_1 + 4I_2)(1 + I_1 + I_2)^2 \right) \right] \\
 &= \pi \left[\left(\frac{7776}{5} + \frac{216064}{5} I_1 + \frac{24992}{5} I_2 - 72 + 3520I_1 + 584I_2 - 1120I_1 - 256I_2 \right) \right. \\
 &\quad \left. - \left(\frac{1}{5} + \frac{211}{5} I_1 + \frac{31}{5} I_2 - \frac{1}{3} + 55I_1 + \frac{25}{3} I_2 - 56I_1 - 4I_2 \right) \right] \\
 &= \pi \left[\left(\frac{7416}{5} + \frac{228064}{5} I_1 + \frac{26632}{5} I_2 \right) - \left(\frac{-2}{15} + \frac{206}{5} I_1 + \frac{158}{15} I_2 \right) \right] \\
 &= \left(\frac{4450}{3} + 45654I_1 + \frac{80054}{15} I_2 \right) \pi > 0
 \end{aligned}$$

Where:

$$\frac{4450}{3} > 0, \frac{4450}{3} + 45654 + \frac{80054}{15} > 0 \text{ and } \frac{4450}{3} + \frac{80054}{15} > 0$$

5. Conclusions

Integration is a tool for understanding cumulative changes, and through it, we can deal with real-life problems that are difficult to solve using ordinary algebraic methods. It is a fundamental pillar in everything related to analysis, prediction, design, and optimization, this is what led us to study the applications of definite 2-refined neutrosophic integrals. The most important of these applications, volumes of 2-refined neutrosophic revolution, length of 2-refined neutrosophic curve, area between two 2-refined neutrosophic curves and the area under 2-refined neutrosophic curves. Where each instance explained with specific examples.

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